

```

public class Inventory {
    private static class Item {
        String name;
        double price;

        Item(String name, double price) {
            this.name = name;
            this.price = price;
        }
    }

    private List<Item> items;

    public Inventory() {
        items = new ArrayList<>();
    }

    public void addItem(String name, double price) {
        if (name != null && !name.isEmpty() && price >= 0) {
            items.add(new Item(name, price));
        }
    }

    public double calculateTotalValue() {
        double total = 0;
        for (Item item : items) {
            total += item.price;
        }
        return total;
    }

    public String findMostExpensive() {
        if (items.isEmpty()) return null;

        Item mostExpensive = items.get(0);

        for (Item item : items) {
            if (item.price > mostExpensive.price) {
                mostExpensive = item;
            }
        }
        return mostExpensive.name + " ($" + mostExpensive.price + ")";
    }

    public static void main(String[] args) {

```

```
Inventory inv = new Inventory();

inv.addItem("Pen", 0.0);
inv.addItem("BadItem", -10.0);
inv.addItem("Laptop", 1000.0);
inv.addItem("TV", 1000.0);

System.out.println("Count: " + inv.items.size());
System.out.println("Max: " + inv.findMostExpensive());
}
}
```